

SOCIAL NETWORKS AS A TOOL FOR LEARNING ENGLISH

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Abstract. *Today, the level of knowledge of the English language is required from personnel working in every field. Therefore, the issue of language learning has become the most urgent topic of the time. In this regard, the Internet, mainly social networks, have come to the fore with their level of activity. The comments in this article focus on social networks as a tool for learning English.*

Keywords: *social networks, English, language learning, modern technologies, busuu.com, LinguaLeo.*

It is known that the beginning of the 3rd millennium is characterized by the rapid development of computer and network technologies. Initially, they were created to solve specialized practical problems and were available only to a narrow circle of specialists. Currently, these technologies are widespread and have clear social characteristics, the most typical of which are called social networks.

If the first wave of the Internet mainly contributed to the vertical transfer of information, the modern Internet in general and social networks in particular are characterized by the development of horizontal relations: work on social relations; means friendship. Social media is not a new concept or knowledge. Like the Internet, it has gone through certain stages of its history of creation and development. It is considered permissible to dwell on this issue below.

We know that the Internet appeared in the second half of the last century and began its development. In these years, that is, in the 69th year of the 20th century, social networks appeared simultaneously with the Internet. One of the earliest social networking resources was created in 1995 by Randy Konrads, a network called Classmates.com. Thanks to this site, which translates as classmates, users have the opportunity to reconnect with former classmates, find work colleagues and friends. The network is still active today and has over 50 million users in the US and Canada.

Today, almost all higher education institutions are equipped with computer rooms, which allows wide use of the Internet in foreign language classes. With the help of the Internet and various social networks, the user can solve a number of practical problems: develop reading skills and competencies using global network materials; improve writing skills; expand vocabulary; work on pronunciation; formation of students' motivation to learn English. Students can participate in tests, contests and quizzes, online contests, chats, video conferences, etc. Modern technologies make lessons more interesting, informative, colorful and effective.

Thanks to the Internet, students can establish and maintain business relations with their peers in English-speaking countries, expand their worldview, learn the culture, traditions and customs of the language country they are studying through communication. able to learn. Social networking has the same advantages. The following advantages of using the social network as a learning platform can be distinguished:

A familiar environment for students.

A person appears in a social network under his name and surname.

Wiki technology allows all network participants to create a network of educational content.

Opportunity for cooperation.

Forum, availability of chat.

Each student-participant can create his own blog, like an electronic notebook.

The activity of the participants is monitored through the feed of friends

With the help of social networks, users can not only find a job, but also have optimal conditions for various leisure activities and self-education. In this regard, foreign experts who study and research founts say that self-management is becoming a trend not only in the field of corporate education, but also in personnel training in general. First of all, this is an opportunity to learn foreign languages through social networks. Previously, only some language courses gave students the opportunity to communicate with foreign speakers on a regular basis. Today, it is possible to learn a foreign language independently by communicating in specialized resources. Currently, the largest of them are Livemocha.com (more than 8 million users and 38 languages according to the network itself) and Soziety.com. It is not an exaggeration.

Livemocha is a popular American social network based on the principle: help others, they will help you!

If the program fails to check some tasks, they will be analyzed by native speakers (meaning American English here!). Several stages of language learning have been developed. Each stage consists of five lessons. Each lesson includes four mandatory tasks: learning new vocabulary, strengthening the learned material, written and oral parts.

busuu.com is a virtual language learning community created by 39-year-old Adrian from Liechtenstein and 34-year-old Bernard from Austria. Both of them are fluent in three languages and don't stop there. Based on their experience, they created an alternative way of learning foreign languages. The creators of the site adhere to three basic rules: lessons are taught by native speakers, use original text, audio and video materials, and do not charge tuition.

Each member of society not only learns a foreign language, but also helps everyone to learn their mother tongue. The site has more than 150 lessons covering a variety of topics and grammar tasks that teach the most important grammar rules. All lessons are accompanied by video and audio recordings.

LinguaLeo is a site based on this service game methodology. The main character is a lion cub named Leo. You have to feed the lion cub at a certain time, that is, by going to the website and completing various educational tasks. There is also an option where the user can add friends. The base of video, audio and text materials is called jungle. Each project participant should determine their level of knowledge and how much time they want to devote to learning. Based on this information, a progress chart is created, with the help of which the user can monitor his progress and determine the optimal number of lessons. More than 500,000 users are registered on this site.

The Edu-Station.ru portal is a new site that helps you learn foreign languages independently. This portal is designed for learning English, German, French, Spanish and Polish. The main advantage of this project is its simplicity and convenience. The site was developed taking into account all the shortcomings of similar projects previously launched on Runet and the World Wide Web. The site offers comprehensive materials on various topics, video lessons, mini-lessons working on various aspects of grammar and vocabulary, crossword puzzles.

It can be seen from the above information that social networks are also developing rapidly in today's rapidly developing information technology era. This development does not only benefit those who create social networks. Maybe it's to the benefit of every user who makes good use of them. One can be sure that social networks are more convenient, especially when considering the most developed of the family of representatives of foreign languages - English as a means of learning.

In the era of globalization, knowing foreign languages is more important than ever. Everyone should know at least one foreign language in order to have a successful career, communicate with representatives of other countries and cultures, and travel around the world. Traditional teaching methods are often ineffective due to lack of practice and live interaction. In the age of the Internet, one click of the mouse is enough to register in any social network, chat or foreign language forum. Thanks to Internet resources, the user can find many books, films and other video materials in different languages.

Over the past decades, the Internet has evolved from a highly specialized network to a worldwide network. Social networks are a unique platform for interpersonal communication, self-education and modernization of the educational process in virtual space.

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